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“PHARMACOECONOMIC EVALUATION ON COST EFFECTIVE ANALYSIS OF ORAL HYPOGLYCAEMIC AGENTS IN A SOUTH INDIAN TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL”

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes Mellitus is "A metabolic disorder characterized by hyperglycaemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion or insulin action or both". "Pharmacoeconomic analysis compares two or more medication options or strategies in terms of their cost and outcome or benefit". The objective of the study is to assess cost effective analysis of oral hypoglycaemic agents on the therapy of patients suffering from Type 2 DM [diabetes mellitus]. A prospective observational study was conducted for a period of 6 months in the general medicine OPD [outpatient department] of SSIMS & RC [shammanur shivashankarappa institute of medical science and research center]. Out-patients who were diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus and receiving treatment specifically with oral hypoglycaemic agents were included in the study. After obtaining the approval from institutional ethical committee, a structured data collection form was developed to collect demographic data, complete prescription details and other information required in the study. Among all oral hypoglycaemic agents the most effective drug/combination in the region was identified. A total of 100 case records were identified and assessed in which 59% were males and 41% were females. Maximum number of patients with type 2 DM were from age group of 50-59 years followed by the age group of 40-49 years and then from 60-69 years. Metformin showed a highest difference in the FBS [fasting blood sugar] value of 4.30 mg/dl, while in combinational therapy Metformin + Glimepiride showed a highest difference in the FBS value of 5.94 mg/dl. In single anti-diabetic therapy, Glibenclamide showed a highest cost difference with 1233.2%, in combinational therapy Metformin + Glimepiride showed a maximum cost difference of 194.18%. Analysis of prescription data found that the single most commonly prescribed drug was Metformin and the most common combination used was Metformin + Glimepiride. Metformin alone and Metformin + Glimepiride showed maximum efficacy in control of glucose level. Glibenclamide alone and Metformin + Glimepiride showed most cost effectiveness.

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INTRODUCTION

Worldwide, diabetes mellitus has been recognized as the greatest challenge for all health care systems. The care of diabetes presents a high burden for individuals and society. People with diabetes are at increased risk of macrovascular and microvascular complications and are more likely than people without diabetes to have other cardiovascular problems.[6]

Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is "a metabolic disorder characterized by hyperglycaemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion or insulin action or both". Type 2 DM could cause everlasting threat, and damage of the necessary organ, in body, such as nerves, kidneys, eyes, and heart, etc. DM is one of world's leading causes of morbidity and death. Individuals who are diagnosed with diabetes mellitus are more prone to cardiovascular problem than their counterpart without diabetes mellitus.[2]

Six different oral medication classes have been approved by the Food and Drug Administration for the treatment of type 2 diabetes. These include biguanides (eg., Metformin), sulfonylureas (eg., Glipizide, Glyburide), alpha-glucosidase inhibitors (eg., Acarbose), thiazolidinediones (eg., Rosiglitazone, Pioglitazone), meglitinides (eg., Repaglinide, Nateglinide) and dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitors (eg., Sitagliptin, Saxagliptin). Systematic reviews of controlled trials have found comparable efficacy for glucose lowering across different classes, not with standing significant differences in side effect profiles and tolerability.[14]

In developing country like India, the majority of diabetics are in the age group of 45-64 years in contrast to developed countries it is highly prevalent in more than 65 years of age. The management of type 1 diabetes mellitus depends mainly on insulin, whereas the oral anti-diabetic drugs (OADs) are the first line treatment for type 2 diabetes mellitus. Complications due to hyperglycaemia in diabetes mellitus can be prevented by using rational use of oral anti-diabetic drugs (OADs) and insulin. Rational use of the drugs is a complex issue with a goal that is difficult to achieve, defined as follows: "That patients receive medications appropriate to their clinical needs, in doses that meet their own individual requirements for an adequate period of time, and at the lowest cost to them and their community.[21]

Pharmacoeconomics adopts and applies the principles and methodologies of health economics to the field of pharmaceuticals and pharmaceutical policy.[12]

Pharmacoeconomics (PE) is an essential method to determine the optimized treatment among different alternative available. "Pharmacoeconomic analysis compares two or more medication options or strategies in terms of their cost and outcome or benefit". "PE analysis is termed as partial when costs are assessed and complete when both costs and outcomes are assessed". Pharmacoeconomic consists of various methods of analysis such as: "cost benefit analysis (CBA), cost effectiveness analysis (CEA), cost minimization analysis (CMA), cost utility analysis (CUA), and cost of illness analysis (COI)".[2]

The objective of Pharmaco-economic study is to influence policy formulation and effect decision making, that is to make a person or a group of people change their behaviour and persuade them that a new course of action is a "better" one, "better" simply means that in economic terms, it is more efficient.[4]

Cost analysis is a type of partial Pharmacoeconomic evaluation which compares the cost of two or more alternatives without regard to outcome. Different brands of the same drugs are the alternatives available for a patient expected to provide a same therapeutic outcome. It estimates the cost and outcome in terms of efficacy and quality of life. Analysis of their cost can highlight the phenomenon of "inter-brand" price variation which can put the substantial financial burden on patients along with posing moral and ethical concern.[3]

Cost-effective therapy of diabetes mellitus will not only ensure rational drug use but also reduce patients dropping out of treatment because of cost, thereby reducing incidence of therapeutic failure by enhancing economic, clinical and humanistic outcome of therapy. Complications due to this disease would be reduced and improvement in patients' quality of life would be achieved. Cost-Effectiveness tool appear effective when applied properly in therapeutic decision making. The various outcomes of therapy namely: economic, clinical and humanistic (psycho- social) outcomes are considered.[4]

Pharmaco-economics plays a major role in practice of medicine in once life. Excess cost of drugs has economic impact on patient and patient adherence towards medication usage may be significantly contingent on the cost of medicines prescribed, moreover patients are confusing with brand names of various drugs in the Indian pharmaceutical market. High cost of medicines is a burden on the patient, especially for the treatment of chronic disorder like diabetes. High cost of medicines is one of the important reasons for the noncompliance by the patient, thus leading to poor control of blood sugar level and increasing the morbidity associated with the diabetes. Hence, cost of therapy should be an important consideration in selecting the anti-diabetic drug therapy. Prices of the anti-diabetic drugs vary a lot and prescribing a cheaper brand will be an economically viable option to the patient, leading to increased adherence to therapy in the long-term treatment of diabetes. On the bio-equivalence data. Generic drugs are widely believed to be bio-equivalent and they have same therapeutic effects as the innovator products.[13]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials used:

- Informed Assent Form
- Patient Data Collection Form

Study design:

A Prospective observational study.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee of Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere.

Methods:

A Prospective observational study was conducted for a period of 6 months in the general medicine OPD of SSIMS & RC. Out-patients who were diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus and receiving treatment specifically with oral hypoglycaemic agents were included in the study. After obtaining the approval from institutional ethical committee, a structured data collection form was developed to collect demographic data, complete prescription details and other information required in the study. Among all oral hypoglycaemic agents the most effective drug/combination in the region was identified.

RESULTS

After the scrutiny, using an inclusion and exclusion criteria 100 patients were enrolled in the study.

Table 1 : Details of gender of type 2 DM patients(n=100).

Gender	Total (n=100)
Males	59 (59%)
Females	41 (41%)

Among 100 patients 59 (59%) were males and 41 (41%) were females.

Table 2: Details of the age group of Type 2 DM patients (n=100).

AGE GROUP (years)	TOTAL(n=100)
30-39	10 (10%)
40-49	25 (25%)
50-59	26 (26%)
60-69	23 (23%)
70-79	12 (12%)
80-89	4 (4%)

A total of 100 cases of Type 2 DM patients were assessed and the following age list was obtained : 30-39 yrs – 10(10%), 40-49 yrs – 25(25%), 50-59 yrs – 26(26%), 60-69 yrs – 23(23%), 70-79 yrs– 12(12%), 80-89 yrs– 4(4%). More number of patients was found in the age group of 50-59 years.

Table 3: Distribution of occupation among the study population (n=100).

OCCUPATION	TOTAL (n=100)
Agriculture	19 (19%)
Business	10 (10%)
Government employee	8 (8%)
Daily wages	63 (63%)

Out of 100 Type 2 DM patients assessed, 19(19%) patients were involved in agriculture, 10(10%) were involved in business, 8(8%) were government employees and the remaining 63(63%) were on daily wages.

Table 4: Economic status among the study population (n=100).

INCOME/MONTH (INR)	TOTAL (n=100)
Up to 1000	56
1000-5000	23
5000-10000	14
Above 10000	7

Out of 100 patients assessed, 56 % of the patients receives an average monthly income below 1000 INR, followed by 23 % of the patients receives an average monthly income within the range of 1000-5000 INR, 14 % of patients receives an average monthly income within the range of 5000-10000 INR and the remaining 7 % of patients receives an average monthly income above 10000 INR.

Table 5: Family history of the study population (n=100).

Family History	Total (n=100)
YES	44
NO	56

Among 100 diabetic patients assessed in the study only 44 (44%) had a family history of DM and 56 (56%) have no family history of DM.

Table 6: Duration of the disease.

Duration of Disease (years)	Total (n=100)
≤ 1 YEAR	12
1-2 YEAR	30
2-5 YEAR	34
>5 YEAR	24

12% of the patients enrolled in the study were diagnosed to have Type 2 diabetes from less than 1 year, 30% of patients were having Type 2 diabetes from past 1-2 years, 34% of patients from past 2-5 years and 24% patients from more than 5 years.

Table 7: Co-morbid disease conditions among study population (n=100).

Co-morbid disease conditions	Total (n=100)
Renal System	1
Respiratory System	5
Central Nervous System	2
Cardio Vascular System	27
Hepatic System	1
Metabolic Disorder	3
Ophthalmic	4
Dermal	1
Without any co-morbidity	56

Among the 100 patients assessed, 56% of the patients diagnosed with Type 2 DM doesn't have any co-morbid conditions, 27% of the patients had CVS complications (HTN, cardiomyopathy etc.), 5% with respiratory disorders, 4% with ophthalmic problems, 3% with metabolic disorders, 2% with CNS complications and the remaining 3% had renal, hepatic and dermal problems.

Table 8: Number of patients based on the drugs given.

GENERIC NAME	NUMBER OF PATIENTS (n=100)
METFORMIN	49
GLIMEPIRIDE	10
GLIBENCLAMIDE	8
GLICLAZIDE	4
METFORMIN+GLICLAZIDE	3
PIOGLITAZONE	3
GLIPIZIDE	2
METFORMIN+GLIMEPIRIDE	18
ACARBOSE	1
GLIMEPIRIDE+METFORMIN+VOGLIBOSE	1
VOGLIBOSE+METFORMIN	1

Among the 100 Type 2 DM patients assessed, 49% of the patients were prescribed with Metformin followed by 18% of patients prescribed with Metformin + Glimepiride, 10% of the patients with Glimepiride, 8% of the patients with Glibenclamide, 4% of the patients with Gliclazide, 3% of the patients with Metformin + Gliclazide + Pioglitazone, 2% of the patients with Glipizide, 1% of the patients with Acarbose, Glimepiride + Metformin + Voglibose and Voglibose + Metformin each.

Table 9: Comparison of FBS among study population.

GENERIC NAME	B-FBS (mg/dl)		F-FBS (mg/dl)	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
METFORMIN	176.06	34.37	171.76	34.27
GLIMEPIRIDE	172.8	28.97	169.98	26.89
GLIBENCLAMIDE	164.5	30.74	161.75	30.96
PIOGLITAZONE	147.67	28.22	146	28.29
GLIPIZIDE	165	21.21	163.5	21.92
GLICLAZIDE	177.75	32.37	176.75	27.48
ACARBOSE	202	0	201	0
METFORMIN+GLIMEPIRIDE	183.11	36.76	177.17	36.56
GLIMEPIRIDE+METFORMIN+VOGLIBOSE	200	0	197	0
METFORMIN+GLICLAZIDE	134	14.11	132.67	13.20
VOGLIBOSE+METFORMIN	218	0	217	0

Among single anti-diabetic therapy Metformin shows a highest difference in FBS of 4.30 followed by Glimepiride with 2.82, Glibenclamide with 2.75, Pioglitazone with 1.67, Glipizide 1.5, Gliclazide 1 and Acarbose 1. Among combinational anti-diabetic therapy, Metformin+Glimepiride shows a higher difference in FBS with 5.94 followed by Glimepiride + Metformin + Voglibose with 3, Metformin + Gliclazide with 1.33, Voglibose+ Metformin with 1.

Table 10: Difference in FBS.

GENERIC NAME	DIFFERENCE IN FBS
METFORMIN	4.30
GLIMEPIRIDE	2.82
GLIBENCLAMIDE	2.75
PIOGLITAZONE	1.67
GLIPIZIDE	1.5
GLICLAZIDE	1
ACARBOSE	1
METFORMIN+GLIMEPIRIDE	5.94
GLIMEPIRIDE+METFORMIN+VOGLIBOSE	3
METFORMIN+GLICLAZIDE	1.33
VOGLIBOSE+METFORMIN	1

Among single anti-diabetic therapy Glibenclamide has a maximum cost difference of 1233.2%, followed by Glimepiride with 404.13%, Metformin 321.06%, Pioglitazone 34.61%, Acarbose 28.07%, Gliclazide and Glipizide doesn't show any cost difference. Among combinational therapy Metformin + Glimepiride shows a maximum percentage cost difference of 194.18% followed by Glimepiride + Metformin + Voglibose with 37.76%, Voglibose + Metformin 21.05%, Metformin + Gliclazide 15.08%.

Table 11: Percentage cost difference among different generics.

GENERIC NAME	% Cost Difference
GLIBENCLAMIDE	1233.2
GLIMEPIRIDE	404.13
METFORMIN	321.06
PIOGLITAZONE	34.61
ACARBOSE	28.07
GLICLAZIDE	0
GLIPIZIDE	0
METFORMIN+GLIMEPIRIDE	194.18
GLIMEPIRIDE+METFORMIN+VOGLIBOSE	37.76
VOGLIBOSE+METFORMIN	21.05
METFORMIN+GLICLAZIDE	15.08

Table no.12: Age-Glycaemic control.

Age group	B-FBS	SD	F-FBS	SD	Difference
30-39 yrs	170.4	27.933	166.6	28.035	3.8
40-49yrs	171.92	35.193	168.492	35.169	3.43
50-59yrs	185.423	28.553	181.403	28.163	3.11
60-69yrs	163.913	34.446	160.823	34.581	3.09
70-79yrs	184.333	37.453	180.316	37.960	2.01
80-89yrs	167	45.658	166.65	41.745	0.35

More difference in the FBS values shows more glycaemic control. Here, glycaemic control is becoming poor as the age increases. More glycaemic control is seen in the age group of 30-39 years followed by 40-49 years. Poor glycaemic control is seen in the age group of 70-79 years.

Table no.13: Gender-Glycaemic control.

GENDER	B-FBS	SD	F-FBS	SD	DIFFERENCE
Female	174.10	35.75	170.14	35.61	3.96
Male	175.17	32.48	171.33	32.32	3.84

Glycaemic control shows more effect in females (3.96) than in males (3.84).

DISCUSSION

The care of diabetes presents a high burden for individuals and society. People with diabetes are at increased risk of macrovascular and microvascular complications and are more likely than people without diabetes to have other cardiovascular problems. Thus, we planned this Pharmacoeconomic study in diabetic patients to observe the cost effectiveness of oral hypoglycaemic agents. Assessing this will help improve drug usage, generic prescribing and selecting cost effective drugs/therapy, and expenditure thereby improving health outcomes.

In our study, 100 patients were diagnosed with Type 2 DM and also who were known cases of Type 2 DM along with their co-morbidities were identified after considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria, their cases were collected to obtain the demographic details, diagnosis, FBS reading and the complete drug therapy given to the patient. Complete details on the patient's disease state and the drug therapy was obtained from the OPD card.

A total of 100 cases were identified and assessed during the study out of which 59(59%) were males and 41(41%) were females. Our study showed males predominance i.e., 59 (59%) as compared to females 41(41%) which is contrast to the findings in a prospective observational study conducted by Abdelaziz MSL et al.[2]

In our study, maximum number of patients with Type 2 DM were from the age group of 50-59 years followed by the age group of 40-49 years and then from 60-69 years. The prevalence of Type 2 DM was very less in the age group of 30-39 years, 70-79 years, and 80-89 years. This result correlates to the prospective observational study conducted by Afroz Abdi et al.[1]

Out of 100 cases assessed during the study, the occupational status was found to be more with daily wages 63 (63%) who came from nearby villages for the health screening .

Out of 100 patients, 56 % of the patients receives an average monthly income below 1000 INR, followed by 23% of the patients receives an average monthly income within the range of 1000-5000 INR, 14% of the patients receives an average monthly income within the range of 5000-10000 INR and the remaining 7% of the patients receives an average monthly income above 10000 INR.

In our study, a total of 100 case records of the patients were assessed out of which only 44(44%) patients had a family history of Type 2 DM and remaining 56(56%) patients had no family history of Type 2 DM which is in contrast to the finding of a prospective study carried out by Kannan et al.[17]

A total 100 case records of the patients were assessed during the study out of which 34(34%) patients were known case of Type 2 DM for a period of 2-5 years followed by 30(30%) patients for a period of 1-2 years, 24(24%) patients for a period of >5 years and 12(12%) patients for a period of ≤1 years were found in the study which is in contrast to a prospective-observational study carried out by Afroz Abidi.[1]

A total 100 case records were assessed during the study among which majority of the patients (56%) of the study population doesn't have any co-morbid conditions followed by 27% of the patients had cardiovascular diseases. Among cardiovascular diseases 23% of the patients had HTN as a co-morbid condition. 5% of the patients had respiratory diseases, 4% had ophthalmic problems, 3% with metabolic disorders, 2% with CNS disorder, finally 1% with renal, hepatic & dermal diseases each. These results were identical to the prospective-observational study conducted by Abdelaziz MSL et al.[2]

In our study, a total of 100 case records were assessed during the study , in which 49(49%) patients were mostly prescribed with Metformin, 10(10%) patients were prescribed with Glimpiride, 8(8%) patients were prescribed with Glibenclamide, 4(4%) patients were prescribed with Gliclazide, 3(3%) patients were prescribed with Pioglitazone, 2(2%) patients were prescribed with Glipizide and 1(1%) patients were prescribed with Acarbose . This result correlates to the prospective-observational study conducted by Afroz Abidi et al.[1]

A total of 100 case records were assessed during the study in which 3(3%) patients were prescribed with Metformin + Gliclazide, 2(2%) patients were prescribed with Metformin + Glimepiride, 1(1%) patient was prescribed with Glimepiride + Metformin + Voglibose and Voglibose + Metformin. This result can be correlated with a study conducted by Ankush Tiwari et al.[8]

Out of 77 single drug therapies, Metformin shows a maximum difference in FBS value with 4.30 mg/dl followed by Glimepiride with 2.82mg/dl, Glibenclamide with 2.75mg/dl, Pioglitazone with 1.67mg/dl, Glipizide with 1.5mg/dl, Gliclazide & Acarbose with 1 mg/dl. Among 23 combinational therapies, Metformin + Glimepiride shows a maximum difference in FBS value with 5.94 mg/dl, Glimepiride + Metformin + Voglibose with 3 mg/dl, Metformin + Gliclazide with 1.33mg/dl, Voglibose + Metformin with 1mg/dl. This result correlates with the prospective-observational study conducted by Alti Aparna.[16]

Out of 11 oral hypoglycaemic drugs prescribed, most of the drugs had shown a cost variation above 100% which is not affordable to all patients. Glibenclamide shows the highest price variation of 1233% followed by Glimepiride with 404.13%, Metformin with 321.06%, Pioglitazone with 34.61%, Acarbose with 28.07%. This result was co-related to the study conducted by Nallani Venkata Rama.[13]

Among combinational drugs prescribed, Metformin + Glimepiride shows maximum price variation of 194.18% followed by Glimepiride + Metformin + Voglibose with 37.76%, Voglibose + Metformin with 21.05% and Metformin + Gliclazide with 15.08%. This result is co-related to the study conducted by Abdelaziz MSL[2]

CONCLUSION

Diabetes mellitus is defined as a metabolic disorder of multiple etiology characterized by chronic hyperglycaemia with disturbances of carbohydrate, protein and fat metabolism resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action or both.

Type 2 DM could cause everlasting threat, and damage of the necessary organs in the body such as nerves, kidneys, eyes, heart etc. DM is one of the world's leading causes of morbidity and mortality.

From our study we conclude that:

- The males predominance was more as compared to females.
- The maximum number of patients were from the age group of 50-59 years. The most frequently prescribed single anti-diabetic drug was Metformin and the most frequently prescribed combinational drug was Metformin + Glimepiride.
- Among the single therapy, Metformin showed maximum effectiveness in controlling the blood glucose level, while in combinational therapy Metformin + Glimepiride showed maximum effectiveness.
- Glibenclamide was the single anti-diabetic drug which showed a highest percentage cost difference while Metformin + Glimepiride showed the highest percentage cost difference among the combinational drugs. This demonstrates that these drugs have more brands available in the market as compared to other drugs, thus the physicians should prescribe the most economical brand in the market to reduce the total cost of drug therapy and thus the economic burden.
- Eventually, a strong conclusion revealed from our study was that Metformin was the single anti-diabetic drug and Metformin + Glimepiride was the combinational drug that showed maximum effectiveness with minimum cost.

In most patients, the cost of monthly oral hypoglycaemic therapy was relatively high, and hence there is a need of rational prescribing which includes more generic drugs so that the therapy is economical for the patients. Cost factor in oral hypoglycaemic therapy is important for patient compliance and the clinicians should wisely choose the cheapest brand or the generic oral hypoglycaemic agents for reducing the economic burden and improving the health status. Development and implementation of formulary in all hospitals is mandatory for the physicians to prescribe generic and cost effective drugs.

Conflict of interest:

There is no conflict of interest

REFERENCE

1. Afroz Abidi, Dilshad Ali Rizvi, Ali Ahmad. Pharmacoeconomic and drug utilization study of anti diabetic therapy in a tertiary care teaching hospital of northern India. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 19 Mar 2016;9(3):371-75.
2. Abdelaziz MSL, Shobha Rani H, Ravindranath S, Ramjan Shaik, Mohamed Kasim, Anas Abdul Salam. Pharmacoeconomic evaluation of oral-hypoglycaemic agents at hospital in Bangalore. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences*. Sep–Oct 2015;10(5):46-50.
3. Shubham Atal, Sarjana Atal, Bhagyashree Deshmankar, Syed A. Nawaz. Cost analysis of commonly used drugs under price control in India: assessing the effect of drug price control order on brand price variation. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 27 Feb 2016;8(4):315-21.
4. Giwa Abdulganiyu, Tayo Fola. Cost-effectiveness analysis of anti-diabetic therapy in a university teaching hospital. *International Journal of Pharma Sciences and Research*. 3 Mar 2014;5(3):82-91.
5. The CDC Diabetes Cost-Effectiveness Study Group. The cost-effectiveness of screening for type 2 diabetes. *The Journal of the American Medical Association* [Internet] [cited 25Nov1998];280(20):1757-63. Available from: <http://jama.jamanetwork.com>
6. Christian Diaz de Leon-Castaneda, Marina Altagracia-Martinez, Jaime Kravzov-Jinich, Ma del Rosario Cardenas-Elizalde, Consuelo Moreno-Bonett, and Juan Manuel Martinez-Nunez. Cost-effectiveness study of oral hypoglycaemic agents in the treatment of outpatients with type 2 diabetes attending a public primary care clinic in Mexico City. *ClinicoEconomics and Outcomes Research*. 6 Mar 2012;457-65.
7. Giwa Abdulganiyu, Tayo Fola. Cost-cost analysis of anti-diabetic therapy in a tertiary health care institution, North-Eastern Nigeria. 28 Feb 2014;6(2):281-86.
8. Ankush Tiwari and Pramila Yadav. Pharmaco-economic study of anti-diabetic drugs. *International Journal of Management and Applied Science*. 24 May 2015;36-38.
9. Tri Murti Andayani, Ike Imaningsih. Cost analysis of anti-diabetic drugs for diabetes mellitus outpatient in Kodya Yogyakarta Hospital. *Malaysian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2007;5(1):19-23.
10. Shuyan Gu, Zhiliu Tang, Lizheng Shi, Monika Sawhney, Huimei Hu, Hengjin Dong. Cost-Minimization Analysis of Metformin and Acarbose in Treatment of Type 2 Diabetes. *Value in Health Regional Issues*. 12 May 2015;6:84-88.
11. Nisharani B Jadhav, Manisha S Bhosale, Charles V Adhav. Cost analysis study of oral anti-diabetic drugs available in Indian market. *International Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences*. 16 Dec 2012;2(1):63-69.
12. Shah Jainam V, Patni Kalyani N, Deshpande Shrikalp S. Pharmacoeconomic Evaluation, Cost Minimization Analysis of Anti - Diabetic Therapy in Gujarat. *International Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences*. 2016;5(3):34-43.
13. Nallani Venkata Rama Rao, Bollu Mounica Chowdary, T. Mercy Mergaret, Ramarao Nadendla. Cost Analysis Study of Oral Anti-Diabetic Drugs Available in Indian Government Generic (Jan Aushadhi, Jeevandhara) Drugs and Brand Drugs Market in Rural/Urban Area of Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 26 Apr 2015;4(5):2201-10.
14. Nihar R. Desai, William H. Shrank, Michael A. Fischer, Jerry Avorn, Joshua N. Liberman, Sebastian Schneeweiss, Juliana Pakes, Troyen A. Brennan, Niteesh K. Choudhry. Patterns of Medication Initiation in Newly Diagnosed Diabetes Mellitus: Quality and Cost Implications. *The American Journal of Medicine*. Mar 2012;125(3):302.e1-e7.
15. P. Clarke, A. Gray, A. Adler, R. Stevens, M. Raikou, C. Cull, I. Stratton, R. Holman, UKPDS Group. Cost-effectiveness analysis of intensive blood-glucose control with Metformin in overweight patients with type II diabetes (UKPDS No. 51). *Diabetologia*. 2001;44(3):298-304.
16. Alti Aparna, Semma Pushpa Latha, Gopalgari Lakshmi Nagarjun, Galammagari Nagaraju, C. Gopinath, P. Murali Madhav. A Study on Drug Utilization Pattern and Effectiveness of Oral Hypoglycemic Agents in Diabetes Mellitus. *PharmaTutor*. 2015; 3(7):31-37.
17. Kannan, Arshad, Senthil Kumar. A study on drug utilization of oral hypoglycemic agents in type 2 diabetic patients. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 30 Aug 2011;4(4):60-64.
18. Udaya M. Kabadi. Comparative efficacy between Glimepiride and Metformin in preventing progression of prediabetes to type 2 diabetes. *Journal of Diabetes Mellitus*. 26 Jun 2013;3(3):129-133.
19. Hongmei Zhu, Shuang Zhu, Xiuqian Zhang, Yang Guo, Yunzhen Shi, Zhimin Chen, Siu-wai Leung. Comparative efficacy of Glimepiride and Metformin in monotherapy of type 2 diabetes mellitus : meta - analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Diabetology & metabolic syndrome*. 2013;5:70.
20. Premlata Das, Balbhadra Prasad Das, Gajendra Prasad Rauniar, Ranendra Kumar Roy , Sanjib Kumar Sharma. Drug utilization pattern and effectiveness analysis in diabetes mellitus at a tertiary care centre in Eastern Nepal. *Indian J Physiol Pharmacol*. 2011;55(3):272-80.
21. Khushali G. Acharya, Kartik N. Shah, Nilay D. Solanki, Devang A. Rana. Evaluation of anti-diabetic prescriptions, cost and adherence to treatment guidelines : A prospective, cross-sectional study at a tertiary care teaching hospital. *Journal of Basic and Clinical Pharmacy*. 2013;4(4):82-87.
22. Sanjeev Sharma, Shikha Agrawal, Hitesh Mishra, F A Khan. Evaluation of the utilization of oral hypoglycaemic drugs in diabetic type 2 outpatient clinic of a teaching hospital in North India. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Bio-science*. 2013;2(3):248-59.
23. Anna Paula de Sá Borges, Camilo Molino Guidoni, Osvaldo de Freitas, Leonardo Regis Leira Pereira. Economic evaluation of outpatients with type 2 diabetes mellitus assisted by a pharmaceutical care service. *Arq Bras Endocrinol Metab*. 2011;55/9:686-91.

24. Suphachai Chirakup, Nathorn Chaiyakunapruk, Usa Chaikledkeaw, Petcharat Pongcharoensuk, Boonsong Ongphiphadhanakul, Stephane Roze, William J. Valentine, Andrew J. Palmer. Cost-Effectiveness Analysis of Thiazolidinediones in Uncontrolled Type 2 Diabetic Patients Receiving Sulfonylureas and Metformin in Thailand. *International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research*. 2008;2:S43-S51.
25. Sahil Shah, Samadhan Shelke, Priyanka Annaso Patil, CS. Mgdum. A study on drug utilization pattern of anti-diabetic drugs in rural areas of Islampur and Kasegaon at Maharashtra. *International Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Chemistry*. 2017;7(1):60-62.
26. Himanshu Joshi, Rajina Mary, Gururaja M. Padil, Chakrakodi S. Shastry, Rahul Pathak. Investigation of In-Patient Prescribing Patterns of Oral Anti-diabetic Drugs in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital. *African Journal of Pharmacology and Therapeutics*. 2013;2(2):54-58.
27. Ralph A. Defronzo, Anita M. Goodman, and the Multicenter Metformin study group. Efficacy of Metformin in patients with non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. *The New England Journal of Medicine*. 31 Aug 1995;333(9):541-49.
28. A. Ramachandran, C. Snehalatha, Vijay Viswanathan. Burden of type 2 diabetes and its complications - The Indian Scenario. *Current Science*. 25 Dec 2002;83(12): 1471-476.
29. JD Kesavadev, KR Short, K Sreekumaran Nair. Diabetes in old age : an emerging epidemic. *Journal of Association of Physicians in India*. Nov 2003;51:1083-094.
30. T. R. Harrison. *Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine*. 18 th ed. McGraw Hill medical; 2012. Chapter 344, Diabetes Mellitus; p. 2968-3002.

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